

TOWARDS A DAMAGE TOLERANCE PHILOSOPHY FOR COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Damage sources for laminated composite materials include those associated with manufacturing, assembly, and in-service use. Of these sources of damage, in-service impact loadings are considered to be a most severe loading condition, particularly for polymer matrix composites used in aircraft components.

The establishment of a definition for the damage tolerance of composite materials requires an understanding of the damage associated with such loading conditions. The current concepts of damage tolerance rely upon experience evolved from the aerospace industry, which are driven by a design philosophy encompassing the safety and integrity of the structural system in the presence of an acceptable level of damage. In this paper, the important parameters associated with the damage tolerance of composite materials subjected to low-velocity impact are examined. Critical elements which should be addressed in order to establish an appropriate framework for damage tolerance design concepts are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

One of the principal design drivers associated with the use of composites as primary structural members is the issue of damage tolerance [1-4]. Fundamental to the construction of a damage tolerant design philosophy is developing an understanding of composite structural performance in the presence of defects or damage. Since advanced composites have had their major application in aircraft components, damage tolerance specifications have been

introduced principally in the aerospace area. This is a direct reflection of the safety requirements for such structures. In particular, the basis for composite design specifications have evolved from those which have been established for metallic structures as cited in MIL-A-83444, with support requirements for testing in MIL-STD-1530A. It is of interest to note that these specifications pay attention to the problem of cracks in metals. However, this is not the key damage tolerance measure for advanced composites. For continuous fiber laminated composites, it has been observed that in service impact loading plays, a major role in producing defects, primarily in the form of delamination. Such defects may not be visually detectable on the surface of the material/structure but may cause considerable internal damage. This latter event can lead to potential failures at loads considerably less than the structural undamaged strength. All defect types create problems; however, impact induced events, which produce matrix cracking, delamination, and fiber fracture, remain the critical issue in composite damage tolerant design. Thus, a basic tenant of damage tolerant design should include the following:

- The acceptance that damage will occur
- A need to assess the extent of damage
- The need for a retained residual strength of the damaged structure

On the basis of the above tenants, it is anticipated that composite structures should maintain lifetime design loads in a damaged condition up to the condition where a barely visible damage state is detectable. In order to simulate this condition, an approach intro-

duced by the aerospace industry is to introduce quantifiable measures of damage as threshold levels for an assumed non-detectable damage event. Two such measures follow:

- A prescribed impact energy level
- A visual damage level

In particular, a damage level of 0.10 inches is used as a visible damage threshold while a prescribed 100 ft-lb energy level is considered as the energy threshold. These thresholds, as selected, are considered to represent damage levels which would ensure a safety level equivalent to or greater than that for metal structures. This can be shown schematically in Figure 1, which shows a plot of visual damage versus impact energy, with composite thickness as a parameter. The indentation depth as a fixed number cannot be uniquely specified for a given impact energy level because of variations in composite thickness and corresponding composite stiffness. For example, using Figure 1 and selecting the visible damage level X related to a prescribed indentation, this threshold is seen to interact with the impact energy levels E₁, E₂, E₃, and E₄, respectively, as one shifts towards relatively thicker composites. This then suggests that any search for a unique damage tolerance identification should include other parameters such as thickness in addition to indentation depth and prescribed energy levels. Presently, such criteria are being evolved not only in the aerospace areas, but within the composite community at large. These criteria may vary from application to application.

One such example, which again raises issue with prescribed threshold levels as parameters for non-detectable damage events, occurs in the following application. Consider a gas pipeline, of composite material construction, which may be subjected to an impact event associated with third party damage. It is entirely possible that the pipe may meet quantifiable threshold levels for a non-detectable damage event, however, the sharpness of the imprint of the impactor may produce a failure of the pipe due to the occurrence of an immediate or delayed leak. This then would constitute a failure of the system, even though threshold criteria had been met. This in turn leads to the importance of distinguishing between surface and interior damage.

As another example, the selection of an energy threshold level of 100 ft-lb of imparted energy

to a structural member is to be questioned. Specifically, for a fixed composite structure, a 1 lb. weight producing 100 ft. lb. of impact energy imports one damage state, while a 100 lb. weight producing the same 100 ft. lb. of energy imparts a second damage state. This leads to the importance of knowing in more detail information on the striker/target configurations and properties.

DAMAGE TOLERANT DESIGN

It has been noted that the concept of damage tolerant design is based upon an initial assumption that damage exists and that structural design is modeled on the basis of the presence of an assumed damage level. Damage size and location as issues are specified by the authority, user, or owner of the material/structure. As an example, the size selected to represent the damage state can be arbitrary when the location is fixed so as to focus on a critical area. The location site selected to represent a critical damage state may not always be in the most logical and representative section.

As mentioned, of the typical damage sources, the in-service impact damage source represents a severe, if not dominant, design concern. A quantitative assessment of the damage tolerance issue for this damage source encompasses the following types of characterization:

- Damage Size and Shape
 - local
 - global
- Damage Type
 - matrix cracking
 - delamination
 - fiber fracture
- Residual Strength/Stiffness
 - material
 - structural
- Residual Dynamic Response
 - vibrations
 - wave propagation
 - repeated impact

One can see from the categories listed above, that the damage tolerance issue involves measurements of key residual material/structural characteristics. The material versus structural aspects are really interactive and, hence, may not be clearly distinguished under many practical situations. Material degradation does effect the structural performance in general, however, whether this effect is significant or

not depends on many geometrical and loading factors. In order to arrive at an appropriate criteria for damage tolerance, knowledge of the residual characteristics of the material/structure appear to be most important.

MEASURES TO ASSESS DAMAGE TOLERANCE

For quantitative evaluation of damage tolerance of composite structural elements, identification of some damage measures becomes essential. These measures can be multiple in nature, and their appropriateness for practical situations may be both material and application specific. If it is assumed that a structural composite will be subjected to predominantly compressive loadings during its service life; the question arises as to what characteristics represent an appropriate measure or measures that can be used to assess the damage tolerance state of such a component. The degradation of the compressive stiffness and strength due to impact damage and their effects on the structural performance such as buckling may be considered as appropriate measures, provided no further damage growth takes place during the remaining service life of that component. This example of a measure can be classified as a load-driven or application-driven measure. One should recognize the fact that for a given structural component, introduction of a damage state may effect all material and structural characteristics and to different degrees. However, the issues related to severity or criticality of these effects may involve a need to consider safety and reliability as opposed to those directly related to change of material and structural characteristics. With such interactive elements present in the damage tolerance concept, it is no surprise that a unifying singular damage tolerance criterion has emerged and, thus, it appears that a criterion reflecting a multi-faceted approach may be more meaningful. The following type of measures appear to be important:

- A) Damage size
- B) Residual strength/stiffness
 - i) compression
 - ii) tension
 - iii) bending
 - iv) shear
- C) Residual dynamic response
 - i) vibrations
 - ii) wave propagation.

As an illustrative example, one such measure, that of damage size is discussed.

DAMAGE SIZE

One measure used to assess damage tolerance is related to the size of the damaged area in a laminated composite component. The damage states mentioned earlier can be illustrated in Figure 2, where the effect of impact energy as related to the type of damage state is plotted. The damage states identified relate to both visible and non-visible defects. Specifically, at very low impact velocities, no damage is visible. However, as the velocity increases, matrix cracking appears. As the impact velocity is further increased, the scope and density of the matrix cracks may grow and intersect such that interfacial debonding may occur. This, in turn, leads to delamination, subsequently fiber breakage, and finally, perforation of the target material. Thus, the damage as measured by some geometric measure, first grows and progresses to a maximum damage size and then collapses to a damage state dominated by perforation of the material/structural elements. This latter damage state resembles that of a hole drilled in a material/structural member. It is important to note that the damage size, and damage type observed in impact events, are influenced by a number of factors associated with the striker and target. For example, the constituent materials, geometrical arrangement of fibers, and the fiber spacing may be important factors for the target. A typical example of a data sheet useful for studying the damage development and characterization for composite targets subjected to impact damage of loading should include the following information:

- Striker Properties
- Impact Location
- Impact Orientation
- Load Classification
- Constituent Properties
- Ply Configuration
- Stacking Sequence
- Target Thickness
- Fiber Content
- Target (composite) Properties

As an example, consider the case of a transverse plate impact for uniformly spaced fibers and a cross ply stacking sequence with extensible steel fibers and inextensible glass fibers, each respectively placed in a brittle matrix (epoxy). For the case of the extensible

fibers, a symmetrical damage pattern occurs without significant delamination. On the other hand, for the case of inextensible fibers, the damage appears asymmetrical with significant delamination [5]. For the latter system, delamination areas, as detected by ultrasound and/or radiographs, can be related to the initial kinetic energy of the striker. Some typical data obtained from Liu [6] relating these effects for thermoset matrix composites are shown in Figure 3. Data obtained for other thermoset matrix composites as well as thermoplastic composites, are shown in Figures 4 and 5. For the systems studied and displayed in Figure 5, and for composite plates with similar stacking sequence and thicknesses, the differences in delamination are related to the material properties or mismatch of material properties between the principal fiber directions and the transverse fiber directions in the composite system. Thus, for composites subjected to a given impact energy, the resultant delamination area can be expected to follow that of the general trends in mismatch between the principal and transverse composite properties which may vary up to two orders of magnitudes. The results shown in Figure 4 do not, however, exhibit this pattern. This discrepancy can be attributed to differences in bond strength between the fibers and the matrix. For such systems, there appears to be a threshold level at which delamination initiates [7]. Also, for thermoset matrix composites, a linear variation in delamination area, with respect to impact energy, is observed. A relation of the type ($K = g_1 + g_2A$) can be written where g_1 is a threshold kinetic energy required to introduce a detectable damage, while A is the total delamination area and g_2 an apparent surface fracture energy [5]. While the above relation may be true for thermoset plastics, it may not be true for the case of thermoplastic matrix composites as shown in Figure 4. In general, the following observations seem significant:

- A threshold level for delamination damage initiation is observed for thermoplastic as well as thermoset composites.
- The delamination size increases with increase in impact energy for all the stacking sequences and for both the thermoset and thermoplastic composites. The size, however, is greatly reduced for a cross-ply thermoplastic composite (CK-PEEK) as shown in Figure 4. The parameters responsible for this reduction may

include the increased inter-laminar shear strength and toughness of thermoplastic resins.

- The effects of fiber types and stacking sequence as related to the delamination size can be seen in Figure 3. It is observed that Kevlar/epoxy composites exhibit a relatively large delamination when compared with corresponding glass and graphite-epoxy systems. This difference can be attributed to the relatively poor interlaminar strength of Kevlar composites. The effect of stacking sequence on the total delamination size, as reflected through the number of delaminated interlaminar planes, is still unclear.
- When pre-loads are introduced into the specimen, it has been shown that the threshold level for damage initiation is lowered [8].

In order to determine the threshold kinetic energy at which delamination is initiated requires accurate control of the impact velocity as well as performing a large number of tests. As an alternative approach to the measurement scheme mentioned above, it has been observed [9] that when the kinetic energy of the impactor is just above the threshold value, a drop in the measured contact force is noted. This force threshold, P_i , can be measured during a single impact experiment and has been shown to follow an equation of the type

$$P_i = ch^{1.5}$$

where h is the laminate thickness and c an empirically determined constant.

Another aspect of characterizing the damage size relates to transverse matrix cracking. Such cracks have been observed in the case of static loading, for example, by in [7]. For the case of impact loads, the crack spacing for the front and back surfaces of impacted cross-ply glass-epoxy composite plates has been studied by Takeda [10]. Specifically, the mean transverse crack distance, denoted by MTCD, has been measured on the front and back face surfaces of impacted composite plates using different types of strikers. It has been observed that the threshold level for the development of transverse cracks appears to be independent of the impactor nose shape. Once, however, the threshold velocity is

reached, the transverse crack spacing reduces rapidly with increase in striker velocity. It appears that at some striker velocity, the MTCD approaches a constant value, a saturation limit; this value being of the order of 3mm for the case of (0₅/90₅/0₅) cross-ply glass-epoxy composites. The above trends have been observed for strikers of arbitrary nose shape and length.

In addition to the surface crack studies discussed above, some internal crack studies have also been made by using such tools as the Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM). Post impact interrogation of impacted targets suggests that where no delamination is evident, transverse cracks grow perpendicular to the lamina interfaces, however, at laminar interfaces where a delamination crack exists, the transverse cracks appear to grow obliquely to the lamina interface [6]. Also, a higher density of transverse cracks has been found in regions of high fiber density as opposed to resin-rich regions. It also appears, based upon experimental evidence, that transverse cracks and delamination may occur simultaneously and interact with each other. although transverse cracking has been monitored for many composite systems, there is no consensus as to the threshold transverse crack density and associated energy level. Considerably more work is needed in this area

A summary of the factors important to the initiation, as well as the control of damage for impacted composites, has been studied by Dorey [7]. For the case of carbon fiber reinforced plastics subjected to transverse impact, the damage occurring has been found to depend upon the incident energy and momentum, the material properties, and geometry. Calculations of the energies involved in the damage process include

- delamination energy
- flexural fracture energy
- penetration, energy

Penetration/perforation of a target is dependent upon the incident impact energy as well as the size and shape of the impactor, with penetration perforation more likely for small masses traveling at high velocities.

The above discussion is based upon linear elastic modeling. Another important question is related to what happens when a critical level of damage is attained. For example, in brittle

systems, crack growth occurs until the stored energy is dissipated, while in deformable materials, the energy may be dissipated without damage growth. Since most resin matrix systems are reinforced with fibers that exhibit a linear elastic response, improvements in impact resistance and damage tolerance are dependent upon improved matrix toughness. In addition, the work to failure may play an important role as a measure of the compressive strength after impact which can be expressed mathematically by,

$$CSAI = K \int_0^{\epsilon_f} \sigma(\epsilon) d\epsilon$$

where CSAI = compressive strength after impact.

CLOSING REMARKS

The capacity of a composite material system to tolerate a particular damage state (type, degree and size of damage) without seriously affecting its required functional characteristics appears to be the key issue within damage tolerance design concepts and methodologies. Needed are some quantitative measures in order to determine how serious an effect is, serious in terms of a short duration and/or entire residual service life. The types of questions posed enter into the domain of reliability and life prediction methodologies. Another consideration that warrants attention is the fact that a damage state occurring within a composite system may be more serious in one application than in another. Therefore, it appears that the damage tolerance concept is imbedded within the following two broader areas.

- i) correlations between damage states and corresponding residual material and structural characteristics.
- ii) correlations between residual characteristics and application-specific limiting parameters. These limiting parameters may depend upon a number of considerations such as reliability, safety, long-term service life, potential for further damage growth as well as other environmental factors.

The above limiting parameters are yet to be defined and quantified for various practical situations, and therefore, we may not be able to provide herein the necessary answers that designers might hope for in order to incorpo-

rate damage tolerance concepts into their designs. As closure, a schematic of the key elements of damage tolerance are presented in the flow diagram shown in Figure [6]. Consideration of these key elements are necessary by the designer to ensure safety of the structure.

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Figure 1. Schematic of visible damage vs. impact energy

Figure 2. Schematic of change of damage state with impact energy

Figure 3. Delamination area vs. impact energy for thermoset composites [6]

Figure 5. Delamination area vs impact energy for graphite-composites (Pendulum Test)[13]

Figure 4. Effect of composite type (thermoset or thermoplastic) on delamination size (Drop Test) [12]

Figure 6. Key elements of damage tolerance concepts